

CERTAINTY CNRS DMP

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for WRF-Chem input data and output for CNRS (IGE/LATMOS) in order to effectively manage/preserve data used and generated within the CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for WRF-Chem data at CNRS (IGE/LATMOS) is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

Cloud-aERosol inTeractions &
their impActs IN The earth
sYstem/ No 101137680

Researchers

Jean-Christophe Raut (orcid:0000-0002-3552-2437), Jennie
Thomas (orcid:0000-0003-2243-8137), Louis Marelle
(orcid:0000-0003-4925-0046)

Organizations

IGE Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement, CNRS,
Atmospheres Laboratory Environments, Observations
Spatiales

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: CERTAINTY CNRS DMP

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for WRF-Chem input data and output for CNRS (IGE/LATMOS) in order to effectively manage/preserve data used and generated within the CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for WRF-Chem data at CNRS (IGE/LATMOS) is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Researchers:

Jean-Christophe Raut (orcid:0000-0002-3552-2437)

Jennie Thomas (orcid:0000-0003-2243-8137)

Louis Marelle (orcid:0000-0003-4925-0046)

Organizations:

IGE Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement

CNRS

Atmospheres Laboratory Environments, Observations Spatiales

Contact: Jennie Thomas

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission||EC

Grants: Cloud-aERosol inTeractions & their impActs IN The earth sYstem

Project: CERTAINTY

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

WRF-Chem output

WRF-Chem is the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model coupled with Chemistry (<https://github.com/wrf-model/WRF>) is a public, community developed model distributed by NCAR and NOAA. In CERTAINTY, WRF-Chem is used to understand aerosols, clouds and their interactions for regional case studies including weather and climate extremes.

This data will be used to:

1. model specify cases of realistic aerosol and cloud properties, including aerosol cloud interactions including remote sensing from satellites
2. Understand how ACI controls and is modified by climate and weather extremes
3. Test new / existing INP parameterizations and their influence on ice and mixed phase clouds
4. Study test cases of polar aerosols and their role in controlling polar cloud properties

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: Dataset

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

Primary dataset in netcdf format (simulation data from the WRF-chem model runs) generated by our team during the project.

1.1.5 What is its format?

WRF-Chem output is in NetCDF format (Network Common Data Form) which is designed to store multidimensional scientific data, encompassing variables like temperature, humidity, pressure, winds, aerosol, and cloud properties.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- Other

WRF-Chem is used as a testbed for studying ACI parameterizations; to understand ACI processes; to quantify impacts of aerosols on clouds and clouds on aerosols; interactions between aerosols, clouds and precipitation; and to simulate realistic cloud and aerosol cases to quantify the radiative impacts of ACI.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

To run the WRF-Chem model, we use a modified version of the WRF-Chem model code distributed by NCAR/NOAA at:
<https://github.com/wrf-model/WRF/blob/master/LICENSE.txt>

Our modified version of the WRF-Chem model for polar applications, developed by CNRS (LATMOS and IGE) is found at: <https://github.com/Regional-Modeling-LATMOS-IGE/WRF-Chem-Polar>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

Also useful for CERTAINTY project partners and collaborators

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

Yes, the software used is distributed at: <https://github.com/Regional-Modeling-LATMOS-IGE/WRF-Chem-Polar>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

For each publication, model run output and code versions will be documented with independent DOIs on Zenodo.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

This is the metadata scheme for Zenodo, which we plan to use.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

Zenodo is searchable

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

aerosol , cloud

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.

Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

Zenodo provides DOIs

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

WRF-Chem output from the EU CERTAINTY project

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset will be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access via our shared storage space. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the Zenodo repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

We will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles with instructions for reproducing the model runs/data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period is a maximum of 2 years.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Data provided through Zenodo will be free to re-use without consultation.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Yes, the instructions for completing our WRF-Chem runs, the model code version, and output are provided with publication.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

We will compress files to fit within Zenodo size limits, which is free of charge

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Jennie Thomas (orcid:0000-0003-2243-8137)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Zenodo ensures data perservation.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Powered by

